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THE PARAMETRIC MODEL OF AN INDUSTRIAL COMBINED CYCLE GAS TURBINE COGENERATION UNIT

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Introduction

In order to evaluate the energetic and exergetic performance of a power plant project, a model defining and solving the energetic media and material fluxes is needed. In the particular case of a combined cycle power plant (CCPP), such model must incorporate equations and computation procedure for assessing the gas turbine (GT) and the heat recovery steam generator (HRSG) performance. Many models have been developed [1-3], however those models are far from being simple and a question arises, whether a substantial simplification of especially the GT model, accompanied by a small model inaccuracy increase, may be accepted. Thus in our study we tried to develop a simple GT model based almost entirely on material and heat balances, followed by a model of a standard single pressure HRSG. We further tried to reconcile the obtained data with the data from a real industrial CCPP situated in Slovakia, which we have kindly been provided for simulation and research purposes. This study therefore deals first with basic theses presentation which further serves in defining the corresponding equations. Afterwards the model CCPP is presented and in the end, the model is validated through data comparison.

Basic principles

The combined cycle power plant is a power plant formed by two power cycles: the topping Brayton cycle and the bottoming Rankine cycle. The combustion air is first compressed in a multi stage compressor; then led to the combustion chamber, where it serves on the one hand as a source of oxygen for fuel combustion and on the other one as a flue gas diluent, controlling the firing temperature and NO_x formation in the combustion process. The NO_x formation may further be controlled by water or steam injections into the combustion chamber. The hot pressurized flue gases are expanded in the one to four stage gas turbine expander, located on the same shaft as the air compressor. Part of the obtained shaft's mechanical work (commonly some 60 to 70 %) is utilized to drive the compressor and the remaining work is transformed to electric energy in the generator. The leaving flue gases may either be directly exhausted to the atmosphere, or their heat content may be utilized for steam production in a HRSG prior to that. The HRSG's multipressure design, used for larger industrial central heating and power plants and for large power plants, is able to exploit the flue gas heat content better than the single pressure one, which reduces the exiting flue gas temperature and leads to an increase in total power plant efficiency.

The combustion air consists mainly of the nitrogen and the oxygen in the molar ratio 79 to 21 and of a small amount of water vapor, varying with the season of the year and the actual weather on the given site. Other gases may be neglected due to their very small content. Thus, the combustion air, due to its composition, may be considered an ideal gas. During the air compression, both its

pressure and temperature increase. The upper pressure utilized in the modern aeroderivative gas turbines is about 4 MPa, corresponding to the compression ratio $\beta = 40$. By considering the adiabatic compression only (though the real compression is polytropic), the C_p to C_v ratio κ and the initial air temperature T_o , the final compressed air temperature after adiabatic compression $T_{f,ad}$ can be calculated by the well known formula (1):

$$T_{f,ad} = T_o \cdot \beta^{\frac{\kappa-1}{\kappa}} \quad (1)$$

Given the ambient air temperature 15 °C, the compression ratio 40 and the average κ value of 1.37, the final air temperature may reach some 500 °C. Obviously, the real compression is polytropic, leading to higher air temperatures. These may in this particular case exceed 600 °C (873 K). Considering the critic parameters of the nitrogen (126.1K/3.39 MPa) and oxygen (154.3K/5.04 MPa), we see that the air's reduced temperature and pressure are $T_r > 5.5$ and $p_r \approx 1$. At such values of reduced parameters we again can expect the air to behave very close to ideal gas. The value of the air's compressibility factor at 4 MPa and 800 K is 1.0157 and at 4 MPa and 1000 K equals to 1.0142 [4] which again justifies the ideal gas approximation. For air containing higher amount of water vapor (the GT located in a warm humid climate zone) the compressibility factor may be a little different but still the ideal gas approximation remains valid.

During the fuel combustion in the combustion chamber, oxygen is consumed and CO₂ and H₂O gases are produced. These gases are generally known as less ideal at ambient conditions, caused by their higher critic parameters: CO₂ (304.2K/7.38 MPa) and H₂O (647.2 K/22.06MPa). However, the gas mixture temperature increases during combustion, reaching above 1400 °C in modern gas turbines, thus the flue gases, despite the CO₂ content of up to 4 mol. % and the H₂O content of up to 18 % (if utilizing the steam injections) still exhibit properties close to those of an ideal gas. Flue gases after expansion to the atmospheric pressure in most cases maintain the temperature above 400 °C, often above 500 °C and therefore can be viewed as an ideal gas. (high T_r value, low p_r value). Having stated the basic theses, we employ another ideal gas property (2):

$$\left(\frac{\partial h}{\partial p} \right)_{T, id. gas} = 0 \quad (2)$$

Component	0.1 MPa			4 MPa		
	600 K	800 K	1000 K	600 K	800 K	1000 K
Dry air	607.5	822.5	1046.8	606.9	823.7	1048.8
CO ₂	1102	1327	1567	1094	1323	1566
Water steam	3129	3546	3990	3036	3506	3967

Table 1. The specific enthalpies of various air and flue gas components in kJ/kg with respect to the reference states given in [5].

This means that the enthalpy of an ideal gas at a given temperature is not a function of its pressure. We can therefore use the enthalpies calculated at ambient pressure for calculations concerning the enthalpies of pressurized air or flue gas. In the **table 1**, the specific enthalpies of air, CO₂ and water steam are shown [5] at the pressure 0.1 MPa and 4 MPa and at various temperatures. As can be seen, at the temperatures of 800 K and above (which is the case of the compressed air at the compressor exit), little difference can be seen in the specific enthalpies except the water steam;

however its influence on the humid compressed air enthalpy is comparatively small because of its small content in it.

The gas turbine compressor model

Considering a compressor, the molar gas adiabatic enthalpy change Δh_{mol} , equal to compressor molar adiabatic work w_{ad} can be calculated using the equation (3)

$$\Delta h_{mol} = w_{ad} = \frac{\kappa}{\kappa - 1} \cdot R \cdot T_o \cdot \left(\beta^{\frac{\kappa-1}{\kappa}} - 1 \right) \quad (3)$$

For less precise calculations, a value of 1.4 is recommended for air compression. However, more precise calculations need to involve the water vapor content in the air as well as that κ is a function of temperature and pressure. If disregarding the pressure dependence (e.g. using the ideal gas approximation), we may calculate the κ value by employing all previous equations and using the appropriate humid air molar heat capacity relations ($c_{p,mol}(T)$) from the equation (4):

$$0 = \frac{\kappa}{\kappa - 1} \cdot R \cdot T_o \cdot \left(\beta^{\frac{\kappa-1}{\kappa}} - 1 \right) - \int_{T_o}^{T_{f,ad}} C_{p,mol}(T) \cdot dT \quad (4)$$

The obtained values of κ for the compression of the air may then be correlated as (5):

$$\kappa = f\left(\bar{T}, x_{water}\right); \bar{T}(K) = \frac{T_o + T_f}{2} \cdot \frac{1}{1000} \quad (5)$$

To complete the relations needed to calculate i-th compressor stage, we must define the compression adiabatic efficiency of the i-th compressor stage as a ratio of the adiabatic and the real gas molar compression work of the i-th compressor stage and incorporate it in the model by the equation (6):

$$\eta_{ad,i} = \frac{w_{ad,i}}{w_{real,i}}; 0 = \frac{\kappa}{\kappa - 1} \cdot \frac{R \cdot T_o}{\eta_{ad}} \cdot \left(\beta^{\frac{\kappa-1}{\kappa}} - 1 \right) - \int_{T_o}^{T_{f,real}} C_{p,mol}(T) \cdot dT \quad (6)$$

It is obvious that the real final temperature $T_{f,real} > T_{f,ad}$ as a result of the partial dissipation of the compression work into heat. The $T_{f,real}$ is equal to the inlet temperature T_o of the next compressor stage. Subsequently we obtain the real gas compression work W_{real} for an i-stage compressor as (7):

$$W_{real} = \sum_i^* n_i \cdot w_{real,i} \quad (7)$$

The molar flow of the compressed gas in the i-th compressor stage n_i may vary, since some air may be extracted from various compressor stages to be used either externally or to cool the first stage vanes of the gas turbine expander, especially for the gas turbines with the firing temperature above 1100 °C. The compressor i-th stage adiabatic efficiency is by some 3-5 % higher than the i-stage overall compressor adiabatic efficiency, since the effect of increased outlet temperature from the i-th stage further contributes to the temperature increases in all succeeding stages.

The gas turbine combustion chamber model

Disregarding heat losses from the compressor and the combustion chamber and assuming a 100 % fuel conversion, we may wish to calculate either the firing temperature for certain molar flows of the air and the fuel, or to calculate the fuel molar flow needed to be combusted with a

certain air molar flow in order to obtain a certain firing temperature. Both values can be obtained by solving the heat balance of the combustion (8):

$$n_{air}^* \cdot h_{mol,air}^* + n_{fuel}^* \cdot h_{mol,fuel}^* + n_{fuel}^* \cdot \Delta h_{r,fuel} = n_{fg}^* \cdot \int_{T_{ref}}^{T_{firing}} c_{p,mol,fg}(T) dT \quad (8)$$

The meaning of the used symbols is as following: n_{air}^* - the molar flow of the combustion air at the exit of the compressor, $h_{mol,air}^*$ - the molar enthalpy of the combustion air at the exit of the compressor, n_{fuel}^* - molar flow of the fuel entering the combustion chamber with $h_{mol,fuel}^*$ being its molar enthalpy, $\Delta h_{r,fuel}$ - the molar reaction heat of the fuel oxidation, n_{fg}^* - the molar flow of the flue gases, T_{ref} – the reference temperature used, T_{firing} – the firing temperature, $c_{p,mol,fg}(T)$ - the molar heat capacity of the flue gases being a function of the temperature. The term $n_{fuel}^* \cdot h_{mol,fuel}^*$ can be neglected when combusting a high calorific fuel (like the natural gas) at the ambient temperature, since in this case both its molar flow and molar enthalpy are at least one order lower than that of the combustion air.

Especially in the modern gas turbines with higher firing temperatures, a portion of air is extracted from various stages of the air compressor and used to cool the first row vanes of the first stage of the gas turbine expander. Thus, the air flow entering the combustion chamber is smaller than the air flow entering the air compressor. Consequently, the gas turbine firing temperature is higher than that calculated by neglecting the air extraction. The extracted air, after having served as the vane's coolant, is mixed at various expander stages with the flue gases and afterwards expands together with the flue gases to the final pressure, thus utilizing its energy potential. However, we decided to omit the air extraction from our model, since the validation data (like the mass flow of the extracted air) are not available.

The gas turbine expander model

The hot pressurized flue gas expands in the 1 to 4 stage gas turbine expander, whereby the shaft work needed to drive the compressor and the generator is obtained. An expander stage can be simulated like a compressor stage. We can define the i-th stage adiabatic expansion efficiency as the ratio of obtained i-th stage work $w_{i,real}$ and the adiabatic i-th stage work $w_{i,ad}$. Consequently, the real obtained work is always smaller than the adiabatic one and causes the flue gases to exit the expander stage at higher temperature than after an adiabatic expansion. But considering the relation (3), the needed adiabatic work for the gas compression and thus the obtainable adiabatic gas expansion work are directly proportional to the gas inlet temperature. Thus, for a multistage expander, the higher gas temperature at the i-th stage exit allows all succeeding stages to produce more work than they would if the work potential in the i-th expander stage were utilized with a higher gas expansion adiabatic efficiency. This fact is known as the “reheat factor” and for large turbines (gas as well as steam turbines) it may improve the overall adiabatic expansion efficiency $\eta_{ad,o}$ by several percents [6] compared to the i-th stage adiabatic expansion efficiency $\eta_{ad,i}$. As a conclusion, for a multistage gas compressor and a multistage gas turbine expander, following relations apply (9):

$$compressor: \eta_{ad,o} < \eta_{ad,i}; \quad expander: \eta_{ad,o} > \eta_{ad,i} \quad (9)$$

The real gas temperature at the exit of the gas expander i-th stage can be calculated by a modified equation (6), where the obtainable adiabatic molar expansion work, multiplied by the i-th

stage adiabatic efficiency is equal to the flue gas molar enthalpy change. The equation (10) does not incorporate the effect of the expander vanes cooling by the air extracted from the air compressor, which, as stated above, we decided to neglect.

$$\eta_{ad,i} = \frac{w_{real,i}}{w_{ad,i}}; 0 = \frac{\kappa}{\kappa-1} \cdot R \cdot T_{f,ad} \cdot \eta_{ad,i} \cdot \left(\beta^{\frac{\kappa-1}{\kappa}} - 1 \right) - \int_{T_{f,real}}^{T_o} C_{p,mol}(T) \cdot dT \quad (10)$$

Obviously, in order to calculate the obtained flue gas molar expansion work, we need to assess the dependence of κ on the flue gas composition as well as on the flue gas temperature. Thus we need to obtain a relationship (11):

$$\kappa = f\left(\bar{T}, x_i\right); \bar{T} = \frac{T_o + T_f}{2} \cdot \frac{1}{1000} \quad (11)$$

In the less precise calculations, the universal value 1.3 is recommended, but the deviations from this value can be quite significant. The corresponding κ values may be calculated by the equation (4), by employing the flue gas molar enthalpy relation instead of that of the compressed air.

Lastly, the gas turbine electric output can be calculated as (12):

$$P_{el,GT} = \left(\sum_j^* n_j w_{real,j} - \sum_i^* n_i w_{real,i} \right) \cdot \eta_{el} \quad (12)$$

In the relation (12), the index j denotes the expander stages and the index i stands for the compressor stages. Subsequently, n_j stands for the flue gas molar flow expanding in the j -th expander stage and n_i means the air molar flow compressed in the i -th compressor stage. The values of the electric efficiency η_{el} may be as high as 97 % and it represents the ratio of the produced electricity to the net gas turbine shaft useful work

The HRSG model

The HRSG is modeled using the widely known pinch technique, in combination with the flue gas and the produced steam enthalpic balances. Obviously, in a standard single pressure HRSG, the only pinch is located at the end of the evaporator (considering the flue gas path), which means that that flue gases exiting the evaporator must have the temperature higher (commonly by several degrees centigrade) than the temperature of the boiling water in the evaporator. This lowest temperature difference between the hot (flue gases) and the cold (the produced steam) medium is called the pinch. By knowing the flue gas mass flow, temperature and composition and by defining the boiling temperature in the evaporator and a reasonable pinch value and by neglecting the heat losses from the HRSG surface, we can calculate the produced steam mass flow:

$$m_{steam}^* = \frac{n_{f.g.}^* \cdot \int_{T_b+pinch}^{T_o} c_{p,mol,f.g.}(T) \cdot dT}{h_{steam} - h_{eco} + \phi \cdot (h_{bw} - h_{eco})} \quad (13)$$

In (13), the following symbols were used: m_{steam}^* - the mass flow of the produced steam, $n_{f.g.}^*$ - the molar flow of the flue gas, $c_{p,mol,f.g.}(T)$ - the temperature dependence of the flue gas molar heat capacity, T_b - the boiling temperature in the evaporator, T_o - the temperature of the flue gas entering the HRSG, h_{steam} - the specific enthalpy of the produced steam, h_{eco} - the enthalpy of the water exiting the economizer (e.g. entering the evaporator), Φ - the ratio of steam and blowdown mass

flows, $h_{b,w}$ – the specific enthalpy of the boiling water. The term $\phi \cdot (h_{b,w} - h_{eco})$ may be neglected if Φ is sufficiently small (say below 0.02), which depends on the local water composition and the used chemical water treatment procedure.

After having calculated the produced steam mass flow, the flue gas temperature at the exit of the HRSG can be calculated from (14):

$$m_{steam}^* (h_{eco} - h_{fw}) \cdot (1 + \phi) = n_{f.g.}^* \cdot \int_{T_e}^{T_b + pinch} c_{p,mol.f.g.}(T) \cdot dT \quad (14)$$

The symbols used in (13) follow: h_{fw} – the specific enthalpy of the boiler feed water, T_e – the flue gas temperature at the HRSG exit.

The model of a dual pressure HRSG is based on similar equations, but is more complicated. The computation procedure may be viewed for example in [7].

Results – modeling κ values

The results of the κ values modeling are shown in the **figure 1**. As can be seen, the dependence on the mean compression temperature is a non-linear one. The explanation lies in the definition of the κ , which is the ratio of the molar heat capacity at a constant pressure and the molar heat capacity at a constant volume. The temperature dependence of the both heat capacities is usually correlated by a second or a third order polynomial, thus the same non-linear behavior can be expected for their ratio as well. The influence of the water vapor content in the compressed air on the obtained κ values is comparatively small and can be satisfactorily assessed by a linear dependence.

Figure 1. The obtained κ values plotted against the average compression temperature (considered as an arithmetic mean of the initial and the final air temperature) for various water vapor contents in the compressed air (% mol): diamonds – 0, squares – 1.8, triangles – 3.5.

The influence of the more accurate calculations of κ can be demonstrated on the following example: The initial dry air temperature is 273.15 K and a compression ratio 15 is applied. With the value $\kappa = 1.4$ we obtain the final temperature 592.1 K. The more precise computation yields the value $\kappa = 1.39$ and the final temperature 584 K. Therefore, the needed adiabatic compression work is overestimated by some 2 % using the recommended κ value of 1.4. Obviously, the difference

increases with the increasing air inlet temperature and with increasing compression ratio. Difference of more than 5 % in the needed compression work can be expected for summer conditions (increased water vapor content plus higher ambient temperature) at higher compression ratios.

The results of the κ values correlations for the compression of the air are shown in the **table 2**. and the results of its correlations for the expansion of the flue gas (fuel – natural gas) are shown in the **table 3**.

Apparently, the κ computation procedure is iterative, since the final (compression or expansion) temperature is not exactly known until the κ is calculated and κ is temperature dependent. But without any significant loss in the computation accuracy, the final temperature, used for the κ computation, can be estimated using $\kappa = 1.4$ for air compression and $\kappa = 1.3$ for the flue gas expansion as is thereby shown: Let's assume the dry air compression; the ambient temperature is 300 K. The compression ratio is 30. The final temperature obtained by using $\kappa = 1.4$ in the equation (1) is 792.8 K. To carry out one iteration, we calculate $\bar{T} = 0.5464$. The calculated κ value is 1.376 and the resulting final temperature is 759.9 K. The values obtained after the iterative process are: $\kappa = 1.377$ and the final temperature is 762.2 K. However, in a real multistage gas turbine air compressor, pressure ratios are much lower (the common maximal pressure ratio on one compressor stage is below 1.3) and thus the κ estimation is much more precise and the iterative procedure is not needed at all.

$$\text{Correlation equation: } \kappa = a + b.\bar{T} + c.\bar{T}^2 + d.x_{i.a.}(H_2O) \quad (15)$$

Parameter values			
a	b	c	d
1.4502	-0.1701	0.0634	-0.0878

Table 2. The parameter values for the κ correlation equation (15). The meaning of \bar{T} is the same as in (5) and (11); $x_{i.a.}(H_2O)$ denotes the molar ratio of the water vapor in the inlet air.

$$\text{Correlation equation: } \kappa = a + b.\bar{T} + c.\bar{T}^2 + d.x_{i.a.}(H_2O) + e.x(O_2) \quad (16)$$

Parameter values				
a	b	c	d	e
1.4104	-0.1465	0.0333	-0.0670	0.1940

Table 3. The parameter values for the κ correlation equation (16). The meaning of the used symbols is the same as in (15); $x(O_2)$ denotes the molar ratio of the oxygen in the flue gas.

Since some gas turbines are equipped with the steam injections for delivering the peak power output, we had to incorporate this fact into the equation for the calculation of κ . The influence of the steam injection on κ is not negligible, since the steam injection molar flow may exceed 10 % of the total flue gas mass flow. Therefore an appendix is added to (16) in order to obtain (17):

$$\kappa = a + b.\bar{T} + c.\bar{T}^2 + d.x_{i.a.}(H_2O) + e.x(O_2) + f.x(SI) \quad (17)$$

In (17), $x(O_2)$ is understood as the molar ratio of the oxygen in the flue gas prior to the steam injection and $x(SI)$ is the relative molar ratio of the injected steam molar flow to the flue gas molar flow prior to the steam injection. The equation coefficients a to e stay the same as given in the **table 2**; the obtained value of the coefficient f is $f = -0.0546$.

A similar equation may be obtained for the flue gas κ in the gas turbines fired by other less common fuel types, like some syngases from coal or heavy fuel oil gasification or some low sulphur liquid fuels.

Case study

In order to prove the whole modeling approach, represented by equations (3-17), we tried to simulate an industrial gas turbine combined cycle unit, consisting of a 16.5 MW class gas turbine with the steam injections modification and a single pressure HRSG. We were kindly been provided with real data describing its operation. A data selection has been made in order to choose data characteristic with different ambient temperatures and similar gas turbine power outputs. A summary of these data is shown in the **table 4**.

Ambient temperature, °C	25	25	10	10	-5	-5
Gas turbine output, MW	16.5	11.0	14.5	8.26	15.1	5.9
Fuel consumption, MW	51.1	39.9	47.8	33.7	49.7	29.2
Flue gas temperature, °C	572	505	532	427	521	376
Steam injections, t/h	13	4.5	8	3.5	7.5	3
Produced steam mass flow in the HRSG, t/h	28.5	20.8	25.1	*	*	*

Table 4. The basic operational parameters of the CCPP understudy at the selected load points. * - the steam mass flow produced in the HRSG was increased due to the supplementary firing. The corresponding data were not used for the modeling.

Furthermore, from the manufacturer's [8] specification of this gas turbine we obtained: the compression ratio: 24, the flue gas mass flow (without steam injection modification): 203 tons per hour (56 kg/s). As far as we know, the only employed means controlling the gas turbine output is the change in fuel consumption, thus the compressed air mass flow was considered to be constant, regardless of the gas turbine's output. Unfortunately, the exact firing temperature was not known, although we expected it to lie in the range of 1150 to 1250 °C. Our aim was to obtain the modeled operational parameters (calculated via the above model equations) possibly closest to the observed / specified by the manufacturer and to compare the obtained steam mass flow produced in the HRSGs to the measured values. The considered $\eta_{ad,i}$ value for a compressor stage was set to be 0.87 and that for the expander stage from 0.78 to 0.8. The efficiency of the shaft work conversion into the electric energy η_{el} was set equal to 97 %.

Regarding the results accuracy one has to consider the difference between the ISO conditions and the actual on-site conditions, differing mainly in the air temperature, pressure and humidity. In all our calculations we assume the on-site atmospheric pressure of 99.5 kPa and the air water vapor mole fraction 0.01, since we did not receive the actual atmospheric condition data in the chosen time intervals. It is obvious that the atmospheric pressure can vary as much as 5 kPa, causing the

compressed air mass flow to vary by some $\pm 2.5\%$ which affects all the modeled operational parameters. The variation of the air water vapor mole fraction between 0 and 0.03 may add an additional $\pm 0.5\%$ compressed air mass flow variation.

Model results

The comparison between real and modeled data is shown in the **table 5**. The produced steam mass flows without the supplementary firing could be accommodated without any problem, given the mass flow and the temperature of the flue gases exiting the gas turbines. Ancillary data, obtained during the computations are shown in the **figures 2,3** and finally the obtained evaporator pinch point values are shown in the **figure 4**.

Ambient temperature, °C	25	25	10	10	-5	-5
Gas turbine output, MW	16.5 / 16.4	11.0 / 10.9	14.5 / 14.5	8.26 / 8.20	15.1 / 15.0	5.9 / 5.9
Fuel consumption, MW	51.1 / 51.2	39.9 / 40.0	47.8 / 47.9	33.7 / 33.7	49.7 / 49.7	29.2 / 29.1
Flue gas temperature, °C	572 / 572	505 / 508	532 / 531	427 / 433	521 / 520	376 / 370

Table 5. The comparison of the real and modeled data for the selected load points in the form real / modeled data.

Figures 2,3. The firing temperature and the inlet air mass flow plotted versus the gas turbine output for various ambient temperatures: Blue : 25 °C, orange : 10 °C, green : -5 °C.

The modeled data shown in the **table 5** are consensual with the real ones, except at lower loads where the flue gas temperatures differ by some 6 °C. This may probably be explained by the lower flue gases volumetric flow rate at the inlet of the expander and the following decrease of the adiabatic expansion efficiency, even below the values we took into account as the possible ones. The obtained flue gas mass flow rates (around 50 to 52 kg/s including the steam injections) are somewhat lower than that given by the manufacturer but it remains questionable whether a gas turbine steam injection modification includes some compressor and expander modifications as well or not.

In the **figures 2,3**, we show data supporting our modeling. In the **figure 2**, a steady firing temperature decrease is reported with the gas turbines` electric output decrease, combined with the firing temperature decrease at lower ambient temperatures. This trend is fully compatible with the previous statements and with the expected data. The **figure 3** shows that the inlet air mass flow does not depend on the load, but is quite dependent on the ambient temperature. The mass flow variations in the observed intervals can fully be explained by the atmospheric pressure and air humidity influences described in the above text.

Lastly, the GT flue gas inlet and outlet temperature in the HRSG are shown in the **figure 4**, together with the obtained pinch point values. Only few data are presented due to the fact that at lower air temperatures, the supplementary firing is utilized in the HRSGs in order to increase the steam production.

Figure 4. The flue gas inlet temperature and outlet temperature (both solid symbols) and the evaporator pinch values (open symbols) for two ambient temperatures: Diamonds: 25 °C, squares: 10 °C.

The exit flue gas temperatures in the **figure 4** behave differently from those of the classic boilers. The flue gases exiting a classic boiler are the hotter the higher the boiler load is. Conversely, the flue gases exiting the HRSG maintain the same temperature (although a significantly higher one than that at a classic boiler exit) over the whole output range, or even (according to our experiences) tend to cool down at higher HRSG loads. The explanation lies in the different boiler structures and heat exchange surfaces configuration. The evaporator pinch values decrease with decreasing GT load, which is fully in consensus with the designed state. However, the pinch values above 30 °C are in our opinion too high for a standard single pressure HRSG and a lower value would perhaps ensure better flue gas exhaust heat utilization.

It may be concluded that the presented modeling results verify our modeling approach and due to its simpler structure it may present a viable option for a CCPP performance analysis calculations even without the inclusion of the atmospheric pressure and the air humidity fluctuations. Moreover, considering the accuracy of all measurements and the uncertainty which they bring into the calculations, it makes little sense to develop a more sophisticated model for the GT and HRSG performance estimation.

Conclusions

The main task of our contribution was to demonstrate the appropriateness and usefulness of the ideal gas principles application to a real Brayton cycle analysis. The whole model, formed mostly by heat and material balances in its own, needs just fundamental inputs (like pressures, temperatures and chemical composition) plus a few efficiencies values to be initiated. As has been shown, the development of the correlations for the κ values has been successful and the corresponding correlations were further used in calculations of compression and expansion works characteristic for the chosen combined cycle power plant. It has furthermore been demonstrated that the influence of local climatic conditions and measurement uncertainties could explain the observed variations in the obtained data and that those factors subsequently contest the added value of the application of some more sophisticated computational approach regarding the expected results accuracy. As a conclusion, the problem of model disaggregation is not the most important topic in solving the real industrial problems since it is too probable that some prosaic troubles emerge which then hinder the calculations via a too complex model.

References

- [1] Facchini, B., Stecco, S., S. (1999): Cooled expansion in gas turbines: a comparison of analysis methods. *Energy Conversion and Management*, Vol. 40, 1207-1224.
- [2] Zhang, N., Cai, R. (2002): Analytical solutions and typical characteristics of part-load performances of single shaft gas turbine and its cogeneration. *Energy Conversion and Management*, Vol. 43, 1323-1337.
- [3] Franco, A., Giannini, N. (2006): A general method for the optimum design of a heat recovery steam generator. *Energy*, Vol. 31, 3342-3361.
- [4] *Perry's chemical engineers' handbook* (6th ed.). McGraw-Hill. 1984. [ISBN 0-07-049479-7](#). (table 3-162)
- [5] *Perry's chemical engineers' handbook* (7th ed.). McGraw-Hill. 1997. [ISBN 0-07-049841-5](#). (tables 2-229, 2-242, 2-354)
- [6] Zbyněk Ibler a kol.: *Technický průvodce energetika*, Nakladatelství BEN-technická literatura Praha 2002.
- [7] Liszka, M., Mandfrida, G., Ziebig, A. (2003): Parametric study of HRSG in case of repowered industrial CHP plant. *Energy Conversion and Management*, Vol. 44, 995-1012.
- [8] The website of the Mitsubishi Heavy Industries - gas turbine products : <http://www.mhi.co.jp/en/products/detail/mf-111.html>